

HELP ME RELAX! BIOFEEDBACK AND GAMIFICATION TO IMPROVE INTERACTION DESIGN IN HEALTHCARE

Frank Spillers, Stavros Asimakopoulos

Experience Dynamics-USA, Lancaster University Management School-UK
frank@experiencedynamics.com, s.asimakopoulos@lancaster.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

Biofeedback represents a new frontier in emotion design. Game design and more recently gamification are proving to be valuable design approaches to increasing fun, pleasurability and wellbeing, particularly in healthcare applications. Moreover, healthcare applications may be significantly improved from designs that incorporate elements of biofeedback and gamification. This paper describes the results of a user study aimed to assess the design potential of combining biofeedback and gamification techniques as a way to improve the user experience. We examined performance and stress levels of ten participants while playing Relaxing Rhythms, a biofeedback game. The results demonstrate the need to design more emotionally compelling healthcare user experiences using biofeedback and gamification techniques. However, as our study shows, mixing gamification with wellbeing applications requires careful attention to how the game is designed as well as even if users perceive it as a game for solving health issues, like negative stress.

Keywords: Biofeedback, healthcare, gamification, psychophysiology, game design.

INTRODUCTION

Game design has developed a mastery of engagement, motivation and flow (Cowley et. al. 2008; Sweetser and Wyeth 2005) in order to make player experience more emotionally compelling. Applying design techniques from game design or “gamification” (McGonigal, 2011; Deterding et al., 2011) has spread to enterprise, sales and marketing, and healthcare applications including many fitness and weight loss

websites that offer gamification user experiences (e.g. <http://www.commitie.com>; <http://healthmonth.com>; <http://fatsecret.com>).

Biofeedback has been used to improve emotion design or playability in game design (Kuikkaniemi et.al., 2010) as well to manage and improve clinical outcomes (Shie et al., 2010). This paper explores the emerging opportunities made possible by a mature game design market, the drop in cost of biofeedback devices and the growing desire to leverage gamification to solve healthcare problems.

In this paper, we investigate the practical value of applying gamification to a common health and wellbeing issue, namely stress. We extend the investigation of psychophysiological (Bellur and Sundar, 2010; Drachen et.al., 2010) measurement in game design, by using Relaxing Rhythms (RR), a biofeedback health game from Wild Divine (2004) with an aim to uncover issues and obstacles for improving emotional aspects of user play in healthcare gamification.

Moreover, the use of meditation training and biofeedback as an interaction design tool, and a therapeutic intervention, offers the promise to make healthcare games more successful, as it takes feedback from user’s Autonomic Nervous System (ANS) and can provide feedback to the user, a key element in good game design (Reeves and Read, 2009).

As gamification extends to healthcare products using biofeedback to guide an emotionally robust user experience, the possibilities become intriguing: How can interaction designers create more compelling

gameplay experiences using psychophysiological feedback as design direction in game play? How can healthcare benefit from biofeedback as a way to improve the patient experience? Can healthcare user experience be improved with game mechanics and biofeedback? Can a richer emotional connection with the user be achieved with a biofeedback interface? Can a greater degree of flow (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990) or “synch” (Spillers, 2008) be achieved with the user and the design itself?

In this paper, we seek to examine how biofeedback can aid interaction design in gamification of healthcare applications, specifically reducing stress through meditation and breath training. Section 2 illustrates the use of biofeedback training interventions and its effectiveness. Section 3 describes the methodology. Section 4 presents the analysis and the main study findings. Section 5 describes the conclusions of this work and its particular insights for the design of healthcare products.

BIOFEEDBACK AS A DESIGN TOOL

Biofeedback was first developed in 1961 by Miller (1975) at Yale University. Today, cheaper physiological (biofeedback) devices (Nacke, 2011) as well as growing interest in gamification (Deterding, 2011) have led interaction designers to view biofeedback as having increased potential in game design (Ambinder, 2011). Video games, in particular those that employ biofeedback to enhance gameplay, behavior and emotion, are finding positive applications in healthcare (Kato, 2010).

Healthcare applications combined with biofeedback have successfully been used in healthcare to treat patients with pain (Gatchell et al., 2003), post-traumatic stress disorder (Lande et al., 2010), panic disorder (Shie Bai-En and Tseng, 2010), whereas treatment of mental illness has combined biofeedback devices and self-help programs (Cutshall et al., 2011; Shie et al., 2010). In addition, healthcare games have been used across symptom management including diabetes, asthma and phobias (Reeves and Read, 2009).

In addition, Dekker and Champion (2007) found that biofeedback can positively enhance emotion in game

design. Gilleade and Allanson (2005) refer to using players’ emotional state to influence game design as “affective gaming”.

Biofeedback has also been used to elicit moods to improve products (Spillers 2010), aka biomapping (Nold, 2009) in spatial environments and to detect mood states, aka biometrics (Gluhak et. al, 2007; Hazlett, 2008) in mobile devices.

Motorola and Verizon Wireless have recently released a biofeedback device that combines tracking of heart rate activity with a GPS & accelerometer combined with an MP3 player and graphing software for mobile phones and desktop software. The MP3 player learns which songs motivate users and creates a playlist a user can use to get past difficult work-out situations (Sherlip, 2012).

The popular biofeedback health game Wild Divine has been shown to have efficacy in pilot studies providing biofeedback-assisted a stress and anxiety reduction for nurses and in children with AD/HD (Cutshall et. al., 2011; Prato, 2009; Amon and Campbell, 2008).

A new focus for game design used in this study is to utilize “game metrics”, actual user play data, including biofeedback, as games are unfolding in real-time in order to improve playability and emotional engagement (Tychsen, 2008; Hazlett 2008; Nacke et. al., 2009; Drachen and Canossa, 2011).

MEASURING PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGY

The goal of applying gamification techniques in healthcare is to improve health and wellbeing which can be aided by maintaining physiological harmony or coherence. *Psychophysiological coherence* describes sustained positive emotions resulting in highly ordered since wave-like heart rhythm patterns (McCarty and Childre 2010). The more harmony the system maintains with the user the greater the richness of the interaction. Likewise the higher the engagement, Reeves and Read (2009) point out leads to more influential participation in behavior change.

Drachen et al. (2010) found a positive correlation between user psychophysiological measures of arousal (heart rate and electrodermal activity) and

self-reported gameplay experience. Interestingly, the results of using a mixed-methods approach (Kalyn et al., 2011) in assessing the emotional feature of user experience (Nacke and Drachen 2011) were consistent across three major commercial games.

Biofeedback combined with a game interface was used to increase interest and motivation to engage the patient to a specific therapy. Similarly, the past five-ten years has seen a substantial amount of debate about the nature of user experience in games (game experience), the elements it is comprised of, and various suggestions on how to measure it (Ijsselstein et al., 2007). A lot of these studies are survey-based, interviews and/or audiovisual recordings of the game sessions. The usefulness of these measures in an industrial design process is a subject of ongoing debate (Tyschen, 2008). Biofeedback measures offer another way of measuring user experience, through neurological and physiological reactions taking place in the player (Mandryk et al., 2006).

Combining physiological indexes with survey data holds potential to develop models (function approximator) of specific user experiences (Mandryk et al., 2006; Yannakakis and Hallam, 2007). Game metrics are numerical data obtained from the user interaction with the game software, and form a valuable data source to user experience research and –design, because these data offer quantitative, time-stamped information about the specific behavior of players of computer games. By combining this game metrical data with traditional user experience measures – biofeedback, surveys and usability methods – it is possible to directly link game experience with design elements (Tyschen, 2008).

Biofeedback also reported to significantly reducing anxiety levels among students (McCraty et al., 2000; Vitasari et al., 2011) and in some cases even improving student achievement index in test performance (Prato, 2009). Importantly, biofeedback training has been found to be a powerful tool to assist students in learning to self-generate increased coherence (McCraty, 2005). The training aimed to support, motivate and emotionally engage students who lacked a healthy social and emotional environment (Arguelles et al., 2003). Vitasari et al.

(2011), for example, employed biofeedback training sessions with high level anxiety university students. The psychophysiological arousal measured through beat-per-minute and breath-per-minute. The results showed that students were able to better control their heartbeat and respiration, thus reducing anxiety level through biofeedback.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

For our experiment we used Relaxing Rhythms (RR), Wild Divine game (2004) and the Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen et al., 1988; Cohen and Williamson, 1988). We used the game's biofeedback sensor aka 'Lightstone' device which has the potential to measure anxiety and stress, relaxation, tension, sudden changes in mood, and breathing variability (Dekker and Champion, 2007).

RR uses biofeedback sensors to receive data from users via biofeedback sensors on the Lightstone. The physiological data collected for this study included Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) and Heart Response (HR). In capturing physiological biometrics while users "played" RR, we were able to observe real-time biometric changes during game *Events*, for example, when users practiced raising, lowering, or balancing their energy with breathing exercises, positive emotions, or calming thoughts. Secondary, we used these measures to compare physiological responses of users who have reported high or low levels of stress, respectively.

PERCEIVED STRESS SCALE

The *Perceived Stress Scale* (PSS) is used in this study to measure users' stress levels. The PSS is a measure of the degree to which situations in one's life are perceived as stressful (Cohen et al, 1988). In our study, we were interested in short- term arousal impacted by the intervention of a relaxation game using biofeedback and relaxation training. Higher PSS scores are associated with greater vulnerability to stressful-event-elicited depressive symptoms. Participants completed the 10-item PSS questionnaire on a 5-point Likert scale (ranging from never to very often) about their general feelings/thoughts during the last month after they played the game. Our measure of stress was not intended to generalize to the participant's life in general but more to the experience of game play. Future studies will explore longitudinal

responses to stress and intervention with biofeedback games.

PARTICIPANTS

A total of 10 users based in the US were recruited to participate in the study on a voluntary basis with minimum age 34 years and maximum 60 years ($M=49.1$, $SD=8.08$). Five users were familiar and/or have practiced meditation, while the remaining five users were not familiar or have had experience in meditation practice. Moreover, five users were regular game players, whereas the remaining five did not play games.

All participants were in good general health and the overall general health conditions for the two groups were comparable. Informed consent was obtained from each participant after the experimental procedures were explained.

PROCEDURE

Biofeedback devices/games are used to teach and guide the users in practicing the protocol to reduce their anxiety by looking at the feedback from their own bodies. Users were asked to play three modules consisting of two parts each: a training module and a game activity. The training module helped users learn the meditation skills they needed to use in order to control biofeedback events in the game activity portion of each module. The third module was optional- users were allowed to choose the game from the library of games. Each training session's progress was checked with the Wild Divine Grapher software to look for changes of heart beat and respiration. In this capacity, we combined subjective satisfaction (PSS scale) and objective measurements (physiological readings from heart and skin activity).

DATA COLLECTION

Two sets of data were collected from the participants. On the one hand, we have collected participants' responses to the Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen et al., 1988) to assess participants' perceptions about their stress levels. In addition, we captured users' physiological measures during the experimental session to determine differences among the groups. Participants were explained the purpose of the experiment and the procedure.

Figure 1. User playing the game, LightStone's on each hand detect biometrics captured both by the game and by software on the second laptop.

The quantitative user actual performance from Grapher was used to compare the meditators vs the non-meditators. Secondary, we have captured the game play process in order to better understand the differences between gamers and non-gamers while playing the game and experiencing different problems (see table 1).

ANALYSIS

The analysis took place through a combination of biofeedback measures and questionnaire-based responses. Biometric recordings of the participant's HR and GSR values were digitally recorded and one of the authors observed each participant playing the game and the changes due to different game requirements. Notes were also kept of the participant's comments and his/her reactions and overall experience when playing the game. Users spent 30 minutes with three stress-reducing meditation and breath training followed by three biofeedback games. Users completed 2 training sessions (steps 1 and 2) and they were offered the choice of the third session (step 3). We used 2 biosensors (Lightstone device), one on each hand. Live Grapher appeared at the left hand one from the game itself (both should be equal). We put the live display on the left, since the software didn't allow running them both in tandem. This experimental design allowed us to observe actual biofeedback graphing in real-time during gameplay.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Users' scores in the PSS showed that they had generally reported low levels of stress after playing the RR game ($M=1.29$, $SD=0.49$). Users with no experience in meditation techniques reported relatively higher levels of stress ($M=1.34$, $SD=0.23$) compared with users with significant experience in meditation ($M=1.24$, $SD=0.70$). Lastly, users who didn't have experience of playing games reported ($M=1.3$, $SD=0.63$) similar levels of stress with experienced gamers ($M=1.28$, $SD=0.39$). Overall, users reported consistently similar low levels of stress in the PSS scale after playing the game independent of gender, meditation and game experience. However, we should emphasize that no further statistical analysis was performed on the data due to the small sample size. We aim to perform this analysis in future work.

USER FINDINGS ON RR SESSIONS

All users completed the training sessions with the RR game (steps 1 and 2), which apparently improved their skill in playing the game. Not surprisingly, meditators were able to impact a steady and coherent HR pattern and balanced GSR compared to non-meditators. The training sessions immediately impacted GSR on all users. As the PSS findings suggest, all users felt and reported that they were more relaxed afterwards. However, it appeared that meditators were able to 'self-steer' their GSR bio-events more evenly (see lower graph in figures 3, 5 and 7). Table 1 describes specific user quotes for non-meditators and meditators while playing the game. The main observations gathered from user interactions with RR with clear implications for interaction design can be summarized as follows:

- The goals of the game or the particular exercise, process are important. Moreover, the controls and clear instructions, such as what to move, or where to go next influence users skill in playing the game, and ultimately their stress levels.
- Gamification in healthcare and well-being (e.g. stress reduction) must be carefully designed with minimal 'achievement' and more learning, encouragement and enrichment from the experience (learn the skill) and progressively receive feedback about their biometrics as reward,

and not just *to reward* users, which is the typical approach in gamification.

- It is especially important to avoid 'performance anxiety' conditions for users who have a disease, illness or syndrome and might be more susceptible to game mechanisms, such as exertion (Meuller et al., 2011). In the case of RR, users seeking this game are likely experiencing high stress levels, and play the game in order to learn relaxation techniques.
- Providing biofeedback visualizations and auditory interfaces to the user (from their own biofeedback) is an important element missing from RR. Biometric status, like "energy levels" common in games, can help users understand if they are 'in the zone' and help them learn when they are relaxed and what it feels like to control particular events in the game.
- Since several users were distracted by the medical "celebrity" experts featured in the training, and felt their minds were wandering off on thoughts about these people (e.g. who are they? What do they want?), we recommend that these images should be avoided as potentially stressful for healthcare conditions that might negatively impact user experience.
- Visual design and voices appeared to be a key element of the game, which led users to calming and relaxing thoughts and conditions (see figures 6 and 7).
- Auditory interfaces (earcons) are needed to help users if they choose to play the game with their eyes closed. Specifically, we observed that both meditators and non-meditators closed their eyes while playing- and missed visual events.
- Interestingly, for meditators the game was more playful (game-like) though they didn't necessarily *perceive it* as a game.

In summary, we believe that providing users with their own biofeedback in the design can show users they have the power and skills to play the game. This can avoid performance anxiety, a design goal of a stress-reducing game. Moreover, healthcare games should provide formal (feedback, encouragement and biofeedback) and informal (pulsating, heartbeat and

GSR events) or even surprises (Dekker and Champion 2007) providing great rhythmic interaction with the user (Spillers 2008). Table 1 summarizes user findings.

GAMEPLAY STEP 1: BREATHING TREE

In this step, we observe the Heart Rate and Galvanic Skin Response for a non-meditation user at the end of the step 1 training session. In particular, the specific user showed spikes in GSR from itching her neck, but this arousal leveled out after following breathing instructions. This led the user to focus on controlling her breathing (balloons), rather than following the game 'rules'. The findings also indicated that non-experienced users were more nervous in preparation for the exercises, which caused their GSR levels to go up during step 1. This suggests the need for clear and informative instructions given to the user prior to commencing the game.

Figure 2. Non-meditation user (first game) skin response peaks at start of game (anxiety) then levels with breathing- required to play the game.

On the other hand, the experienced meditator user, took control of her stress response (GSR activity) with active breathing, which resulted in a much smoother breathing control as figure 3 indicates.

Figure 3. Experienced meditation user (first game) with greater control of skin response during gameplay.

Most of the meditators also played over half of the game with their eyes closed and seemed less nervous about the 'competition'. This implies the need to teach the non-experienced meditators how to control breathing, relaxing and take stress lightly. Variance in balloons appeared to be an exciting feature of the game, which resulted in more relaxing conditions for the experienced users but a stressful factor for non-experienced meditators. In particular, meditators found the voice guidance particularly helpful at this stage, however, an indicator of how much time to spend on this step could also serve this process more effectively.

GAMEPLAY STEP 2: FLOATING BALLOONS

In step 2, the non-experienced in meditation user still experienced high levels of stress as evidenced by GSR and HR (see figure 4) in her attempt to learn the game. User described this situation as follows: 'I'd like to feel a beginning, middle and end-like to know when it's going to end'. Moreover, the user didn't like the balloon and couldn't figure out what a suitable response should be and if it would have an effect at all. Step 2 also revealed the need for users to control the visual changes and attain better synch the game (see Spillers, 2008). As the example in figure 4 indicates, this user's HR and GSR were overall uneven on step 2.

Figure 4. Non-meditation user (second game) has less coherence in heart rate and skin response.

The experienced meditator continued to reduce his stress levels during step 2, resulting in a smoother transition compared to non-experienced meditators from step 1. However, the user noted that 'balloons didn't correlate to what I wanted them to do'. Experienced meditators were also able to provide specific recommendations as to how the game design could be improved.

Figure 5. Experienced Meditation user (second game) controls skin response activity remains constant with relaxing thoughts; spike appears when user changes to exciting thoughts.

Figure 7. Meditation user (third game) practicing release of physical tension maintains a higher level of control of skin response.

Interestingly, it appears that more experienced users who control their breathing and stress levels early during the training sessions appreciated the graphics and sounds as well as the background melody as a relaxing factor. During ‘Yoga passage’ the user also was over-excited trying to get it and that ruined it. A common theme that emerged was that balloons didn’t seem to correspond to user actions. This resulted in user lost of focus and control over the training session. We believe this illustrates the need for giving users a playful indication of how they are "doing" (e.g. showing live biometrics as a task performance aid).

GAMEPLAY STEP 3: MAIN PRACTICE SESSION

Figure 6. Non-meditation user (third game) practicing compassion after multiple trainings and maintains a higher level of control.

Experienced users achieved meditation and low stress levels, but they would prefer not to play this game at their computers, because they don’t want to relax there. In particular the HR was overall coherent throughout the sessions, while the GSR started initially high and then leveled out flat. Thus, while HR and GSR were uneven during steps 1 and 2, step 3 showed gradual decline, with spikes only moving when body or hand was moving.

During the main practice session, both experienced and non-experienced users showed more GSR/HR variance due to its difficulty. Based on this finding, there is a need to design steps that are less difficult and result in lower stress levels. This is an interesting finding, which indicates that designers should think of ways to retain the same levels of difficulty for the main practice sessions. This could be possible by providing more feedback and encouragement through short messages to the user, when facing difficult ‘events’.

RESULTS

Based on the user findings, we outline a set of design ideas that can be incorporate in games aimed at healthcare applications. Table 1 provides a summary of main user difficulties on the specific game play and the design features that could support users in this process.

Design ideas	User observations
Step-by-step instructions and training to account for relaxing, non-competitive mood	Lack of instructions and user training
Feedback on visual changes to increase user control	Visual experience was distracting

Design ideas	User observations
Time indication on the duration of the training and main practice sessions	Exercises helped users to concentrate on game play
Provide users with positive rewards	Balloons design was stressful and confusing
Auditory features to incorporate external events into game narrative and enable 'game play' with eyes closed.	Counter-productive to play the game/meditate with eyes open
Explanatory feedback on events that users may find difficult to handle	Game features didn't correspond to user actions
Losing or winning need to be clear in game rules/design	Performance anxiety and user self-blaming

Table 1. Summary of design ideas and user observations

DISCUSSION

Given that RR was designed with the collaboration of three medical doctors (Dr. Deepak Chopra, Dr. Andrew Weil, Dr. Dean Ornish), the effects of the relaxation sessions were expected to be positive. Short duration meditation training has been found to induce brain change (Davidson et.al., 2003). However, in our study, 1/3 of participants reported that they were negatively distracted by the images and names of these 'celebrity' doctors (which appear in

steps 1 and 2, the training phases of the game). We did observe GSR spike up initially but then dissipate; many users closed their eyes during the training sessions.

While users did not notice the biometrics captured in real-time (a laptop with their graphing was placed next to another laptop with the game), it seems that providing users with feedback about their self-guided biofeedback sessions would be valuable to teaching users the healthy patterns of stress management.

Biofeedback as an interaction technique seems to aid the richness of the gaming experience. Dekker and Champion (2007) used the Lightstone biofeedback to feedback game events impacting user emotions and making their game's zombies more frightening (an aspect of the game's fun). Since users closed their eyes during meditation (and even non-meditators told us they thought that this is what you are supposed to do), providing users with feedback about their biometrics would have to be auditory as well as visually displayed.

Moreover, over half of the users in our study wanted to know how long each game would last. Time typically in games is used to increase motivation, tension and exertion (Reeves and Read 2009; Mueller et.al. 2011). We conclude that how time as a design artifact is handled needs be carefully considered in healthcare gamification.

FUTURE WORK

It was also clear from our study that interaction design issues specific to healthcare treatment scenarios need to be investigated further. Gamification "one size fits all" will miss the emotion-specific sensitivities that go along with an illness, symptom or patient population. Mobile usage scenarios might also change context of use and, as such, the design needs for gamification in healthcare applications will require more careful attention in the future.

Another factor for future studies is multiplayer interaction. Preece (2000) and Maloney-Krichmar & Preece (2005) found that online community and sociability has a positive supporting quality to wellbeing and healing outcomes. De Freitas (2011)

places emphasis on gamification in learning as being aided strongly by collaboration and community effects. McGonigal (2011) found herself seeking a multiplayer game to deal with depression, in recovering from an injury. Given that users/patients need sociability in their treatment experience, biofeedback as an interaction design tool offers the possibility to improve the emotional direction of gameplay.

In future work, we aim to long term use of meditation training software to improve overall stress management over time and to explore applications to other healthcare contexts. Moreover, we envisage that different health conditions would require different interaction design approaches to gamification, for example, providing the output of biofeedback to the user (as well as the system utilizing the users biometrics) which enable the user to obtain accurate and timely feedback on the different game stages and their performance throughout.

CONCLUSION

Healthcare applications may benefit from designs that incorporate elements of biofeedback and gamification to positively impact user emotions. Biofeedback in game design can offer a more tailored more immersive, dynamic and calibrated game experience (Ambinder, 2011; Hazlett, 2008).

In RR, we found that users exhibited increased GSR activity by the stress of receiving instructions when starting an exercise. Stress is a powerful arousal mechanism (Mueller et.al. 2011). In game design, stress is usually deliberately employed to boost game play, by increasing tension. Anti-stress games must take care to avoid arousal that is not intentional in design. Similarly, since the RR looked like a game (3D graphics and narrative) several gamers felt anxiety over having to perform- a typical good stress (McGonigal 2011) in a game. Goals and challenges, typical to gamification are also important to consider since they sustain flow and motivation, (Raymer, 2011), in an anti-stress game, they may cause unwanted stress -as observed in several participants in our study.

Designing for gamification in healthcare situations requires careful design choices that need to be

considerate of the patient population sensitivities, preconditions or psychophysiological constraints that would typically be added to game design, for example, music, visuals, time, goals and rewards, We believe the current study indicates that healthcare gamification needs to be inclusive of personalized and situated gameplay user experiences. Biofeedback as an interaction design tool offers the possibility to improve the emotional robustness of gameplay and its events, which in healthcare can more effectively lead to better recovery and efficacy.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We wish to warmly thank all users who volunteered to participate in this study.

REFERENCES

- Ambinder, M. (2011) Biofeedback in Gameplay: How Valve Measures Physiology to Enhance Gaming Experience. *Game Developers Conference*, San Francisco, CA. Accessed December 3rd 2011: www.valvesoftware.com/.../2011/ValveBiofeedback-Ambinder.pdf
- Amon, K., Campbell, A. (2008) Can children with AD/HD learn relaxation and breathing techniques through biofeedback video games?. *Australian Journal of Educational & Developmental Psychology*, Vol. 8, 72-84
- Arguelles, L., McCraty, R., Rees, R.A. (2003) The heart in holistic education. *ENCOUNTER: Education for Meaning and Social Justice*, Vol. 16, Issue 3, 13-21
- Bellur, S., Sundar, S.S. (2010) Psychophysiological Responses to Media Interfaces: A Communications Perspective. In *Proceedings of ACM CHI 2010 Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, Atlanta, GA, 2247-2256
- Cohen, S., Williamson, G. (1988) Perceived Stress in a Probability Sample of the United States. In Spacapan, S., Oskamp, S. (Eds), *The Social Psychology of Health*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage, 31-67
- Cowley, B., Charles, D., Black, M. Hickey, R. (2008) Toward an Understanding of Flow in Video Games. In *Proceedings of the ACM CiE Conference*, 6(2), article 20
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1990). *Flow: The Psychology of Optimal Experience*. HarperCollins: New York.
- Cutshall, M.S., Wentworth, J.L., Wahner-Roedler, L.D., Vincent, A., Schmidt, E.J., Loehrer, L.L. Cha, S.S., Bauer, A.B. (2011) Evaluation of a Biofeedback-Assisted Meditation Program as a Stress Management Tool for Hospital Nurses: A Pilot Study. *EXPLORE*, March/April, Vol.7, Issue 2, 110-112
- Davidson, R.J. Kabat-Zinn, J., Schumacher, J., Rosenkranz, M., Muller, D., Santorelli, S.F., Urbanowski, F., Harrington, A., Bonus, K., Sheridan, J.F. (2003) Alterations in Brain and Immune Function Produced by Mindfulness Meditation. *Psychosomatic Medicine*, Jul-Aug, Vol. 65, Issue 4, 564-70.
- De Freitas, S. (2011). The Gamification of Immersive Learning Experiences, *The Serious Games Institute*. Accessed December 22nd 2011: www.athenaeurope.org/getFile.php?id=1047
- Dekker, A., Champion, E. (2007) Please Biofeed the Zombies: Enhancing the Gameplay and Display of a Horror Game Using Biofeedback, In *Proceedings of the Digital Games Research Association (DiGRA) conference*, 550-558

- Deterding, S. (2011) Meaningful Play: Getting Gamification Right, *Google Tech Talk: January 24, 2011*. Accessed December 9th 2011: www.slideshare.net/dings/meaningful-play-getting-gamification-right
- Drachen, A. & Canossa, A (2011). Towards Gameplay Analysis via Gameplay Metrics. In Lugmayr, A.; Franssila, H.; Näränen, P., Sotamaa, O. & Vanhala, J. (Eds.) "Media in the Ubiquitous Era: Ambient, Social and Gaming Media". IGI Global Publishers
- Drachen, A. Nacke, L., Yannakakis, G. Pedersen, A. L. (2010) Correlation between heart rate, electrodermal activity and player experience in First-Person Shooter games. *In Proceedings of the 5th ACM SIGGRAPH Conference*, ACM-SIGGRAPH Publishers, 49-54
- Dornhege, G. (2007) *Toward Brain-Computer Interfacing*. MIT Press.
- Gatchell, J.R., Robinson, C.R., Pulliam, C., Maddrey, M.A. (2003) Biofeedback with Pain Patients: Evidence for its Effectiveness, *Seminars in Pain Medicine*, Vol.1, Issue 2, 55-66
- Gilleade, K., Allason, J. (2005) Affective Videogames and Modes of Affective Gaming: Assist Me, Challenge Me, Emote Me. *In Proceedings of the DIGRA Conference: Changing Views-Worlds in Play*, 10-16 June, Vancouver, Canada
- Gluhak, A., Presser, M., Zhu, L., Esfandiari, S. (2007) Towards Mood based Mobile Services and Applications. In G. Kortuem, J. Finney, R. Lea, V. Sundramoorthy (Eds.). *Smart Sensing and Context* (4793), Berlin: Springer-Verlag, 159–174
- Hazlett, R. (2008) Using Biometric Measurement to Help Develop Emotionally Compelling Games. *In Game Usability: Advice from the Experts for Advancing the Player Experience*, Burlington, MA: Morgan Kaufmann, 187 – 205
- Ijsselstein, W., de Kort, Y., Poels, K., Jugelionis, A. and Bellotti, F. (2007) Characterizing and Measuring User Experiences in Digital Games. *In Proceedings of the ACE Conference, 13-15 June, Salzburg, Austria*, ACM Publishers
- Kalyn, M., Mandryk, R.L. & Nacke, L.E. (2011) Biofeedback Game Design: Using Direct and Indirect Physiological Control to Enhance Game Interaction, *ACM Press*, 103-112
- Kato, P. (2010) Video Games in Health Care: Closing the Gap. *Review of General Psychology*. Vol., 14, Issue, 2, 113-121.
- Kuikkaniemi, K., Kosunen, I., Turpeinen, M., Saari, T., Laitinen, T., Lievonen, P. (2010) Designing Biofeedback for Games and Playful Applications. In Proceedings of the CHI 2010 Conference, Atlanta, GA. Accessed Dec. 21st 2011: <http://www.eecs.tufts.edu/~agirou01/workshop/papers/Kuikkaniemi-CHI2010-BrainBodyBytes2010.pdf>
- Lande, G.R., Williams, B.L., Francis, L.J., Gagnani, C., Morin, L.M. (2010) Efficacy of biofeedback for post-traumatic stress disorder. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine*, Vol.18, 256-259
- Maloney-Krichmar, D., Preece, J. (2005) A multilevel analysis of sociability, usability and community dynamics in an online health community. *Transactions on Human-Computer Interaction (special issue on Social Issues and HCI)*, Vol. 12, Issue(2), 201-232.
- Mandryk, R. L., Atkins, M. S. and Inkpen, K. M. A. (2006) Continuous and Objective Evaluation of Emotional Experience with Interactive Play Environments. In Proceedings of *CHI 2006 Conference: Novel methods: Emotions, Gestures, Events*, ACM Press.
- McCraty, R. (2005). Enhancing Emotional, Social, and Academic Learning with Heart Rhythm Coherence Feedback. *Biofeedback*, 33(4), 130-134.
- McCraty, R., Childre, D. (2010). Coherence: Bridging Personal, Social, and Global Health. *Alternative Therapies*, Vol.16, No4, 10-24
- McCraty, R., D. Tomasino, M. Atkinson, P. Aasen, and S. J. Thurik. (2000). Improving test-taking skills and academic performance in high school students using HeartMath learning enhancement tools. Boulder Creek, CA: HeartMath Research Center, Institute of HeartMath, Publication No. 00-010.
- McGonigal, J. (2011) *Reality is Broken: Why games make us better and how they can change the world*. Penguin Press.
- Miller, N. E.(1975) Clinical applications of biofeedback: Voluntary control of heart rate, rhythm, and blood pressure. H. I. Russel. *New horizons in cardiovascular practice*. Baltimore: University Park Press, 239-249.
- Mueller, F., Peer, F., Agamanolis, S., Sheridan, J. (2011) Gamification and Exertion. *In Proceedings of CHI 2011 Conference*, May 7–12, 2011, Vancouver, BC, Canada.
- Nacke, L. (2011). Directions in Physiological Game Evaluation and Interaction. *CHI 2011 Workshop*, May 7-12, 2011. Vancouver BC
- Nacke, L. Armbinder, M.Canossa, A., Drachen, A.Mandryk, R., Pinelle, D. (2009) Game Metrics and Biometrics: The Future of Player Experience Research. Panel, *In Proceedings of Future Play/GDC*, Canada 2009, ACM Publishers.
- Nacke, L.; Drachen, A. (2011). Towards a Framework of Player Experience Research. In Proceedings of the 2011 Foundations of Digital Games Conference (Bordeaux, France), EPEX 11 Workshop. ACM Publishers
- Nold, C. (Ed.). (2009) *Emotional Cartography*. Creative Commons. Accessed January 7th 2010. <http://www.emotionalcartography.net/biomapping> emotion in social spaces- cities
- Prato, C.A. (2009) Biofeedback assisted relaxation training program to decrease test anxiety in nursing students. *Ph.D. Thesis, University of Nevada Las Vegas, USA*
- Preece, J. (2000). *Online Communities: Designing Usability, Supporting Sociability*. Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons
- Raymer, R. (2011) Gamification: Using Game Mechanics to Enhance eLearning. *eLearn Magazine: An ACM Publication* Accessed Jan 21st 2012: <http://elearnmag.acm.org/featured.cfm?aid=2031772>
- Reeves, B., Read, J.L. (2009) *Total Engagement: Using Games to Change the Way People Work and Businesses Compete*. Boston: Harvard Business School Publishing.
- Shie Bai-En, J., Fong-Lin & Tseng, V. S. (2010). Intelligent panic disorder treatment by using biofeedback analysis and web technologies, *International Journal of Business Intelligence and Data Mining*, Vol.5, Issue 1,77-93
- Sherlip, A.(2012) Gadget Guru Review: MOTOACTV, Accessed Feb 1st 2012: <http://www.emsexploration.com/wordpress/motoactv/>
- Spillers, F. (2008) *Synch with me": Rhythmic interaction as an emerging principle of experiential design*. In Hekkert, P.M. et. al. (Eds), *Proceedings of the Sixth Bi-annual Conference on Design and Emotion*. Hong Kong, China
- Spillers, F. (2010) *Getting in the Mood: The role of mood in product design and interaction*. In Hekkert, P.M. et. al. (Eds) *Proceedings of the Seventh Bi-annual Conference on Design and Emotion*. Chicago, IL USA.
- Sweetser, P. and Wyeth, P. (2005) GameFlow: A Model for Evaluating Player Enjoyment in Games. *ACM Computers in Entertainment*, 3(3), Article 3A.
- Tychsen, A. (2008). Crafting User Experience via Game Metrics Analysis. *Workshop during NordiCHI 2008 Conference*, 20-22

October, Lund, Sweden Accessed January 5th 2012
<http://www.cs.uta.fi/~ux-emotion/papers.html>

Vitasari, P., Wahab, A.N.M., Herawan, T., Sin, K.S.
(2011) Psychophysiological treatment in reduced anxiety with
biofeedback training for university students. *Procedia-Social and
Behavioral Sciences*, Vol.30, 629-633

Yannakakis, N., Hallam, J. (2007) Capturing Player Enjoyment in
Computer Games. *In Advanced Intelligent Paradigms in Computer
Games 2007*, 175-201.

Wild Divine Project (2004) Journey to Wild Divine. *Wild Divine
Project*, Available at <http://www.wilddivine.com>